

Synthesis of some Newer 2-Phenyliminothiazolidinopyrazolines

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A large number of thiazolidines¹ and pyrazolines² are known for their biological properties. Therefore, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some new thiazolidinopyrazolines with substitution in thiazolidine or pyrazoline ring. Thus 2-phenyliminothiazolidin-4-one and 2-phenylimino-3-phenylthiazolidin-4-one were condensed with benzaldehyde separately to yield the corresponding benzyldene derivatives **1** and **2** respectively. Both the benzyldene derivatives when treated separately with hydrazine or substituted hydrazines gave their corresponding pyrazolines (**3-9**). The intermediate hydrazones could not be separated. The analytical and spectral data of the compounds (Table 1) supported

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹
3	318	80	3 120 (NH), 1 590 (C=N), 750 (Ph)
4 ^a	325	80	3 300 (NH), 1 630 (C=N), 770 (Ph)
5	238	80	3 120 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 760 (Ph)
6	206	90	3 140 (NH), 1 610 (C=N), 750 (Ph)
7	220	80	3 040 (NH), 1 580 (C=N), 760 (Ph)
8 ^b	220	80	1 570 (C=N), 760 (Ph)
9	218	90	1 585 (C=N), 760 (Ph)

^a δ 1.2 (1H, CH), 5.0 (2H, benzylic CH and NH) and 7.2–7.7 (15H, m, 3 × Ph), ^b $\lambda_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 267, 295, 355 and 388 nm.

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their structures. These compounds also showed characteristic Knorr's test for pyrazolines³.

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|---|--|
| 1, 10; X=H | 6; X=H, Y=2,4-(O,N) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ |
| 2, 11; X=Ph | 7; X=Ph, Y=H |
| 3; X=Y=H | 8; X=Y=Ph |
| 4; X=H, Y=Ph | 9; X=Ph, Y=p-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ |
| 5; X=H, Y=p-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ | |

The structures of the thiazolidinopyrazolines were further confirmed by the oxidation of two typical members 4 and 8 by chromium trioxide in acetic acid or bromine in carbon tetrachloride⁴ to give the corresponding pyrazoles (10 and 11), respectively.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on Varian A-60 and A-90 instruments using TMS as standard reference.

5-Benzylidene-2-phenyliminothiazolidin-4-one (1): A mixture of 2-phenyliminothiazolidin-4-one (5 g), benzaldehyde (5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (4 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. After 2 h, the resulting yellow crystals were washed with water and alcohol and then crystallised from glacial acetic acid (5 g), m.p. 258° (lit.⁵ 258°).

5-Benzylidene-3-phenyl-2-phenyliminothiazolidin-4-one (2): A mixture of 3-phenyliminothiazolidin-4-one (5 g), glacial acetic acid (40 ml), fused sodium acetate (4.5 g) and benzaldehyde (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After 0.5 h a clear yellow solution was obtained and gradually yellow crystals appeared. After cooling the crystals were washed with alcohol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid (5 g), m.p. 214° (lit.⁶ 214°).

Thiazolidinopyrazolone (3): A mixture of the benzylidene (1; 1.5 g) and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. After 1 h the reaction mixture became deep

yellow and on cooling the resulting yellow solid was washed with alcohol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

Compounds 4-9 were prepared similarly and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow (3, 7, 8) or red (4-6, 9) products.

Thiazolidinopyrazole (10): To a solution of the pyrazolone (4; 1 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added chromium trioxide (500 mg) when colour of the solution turned grey immediately and then to deep green. The reaction mixture was heated at 80° on a water-bath for 0.5 h. It was then cooled and poured into crushed ice (100 g). The resulting grey solid was washed with water and alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid (0.5 g), m.p. 260°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 260 (NH), 1 660, 1 600 (C=N) and 750 cm⁻¹ (Ph).

Compound 11 was prepared similarly from 8 and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as grey crystals (0.7 g), m.p. 222°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 585 (C=N) and 760 cm⁻¹ (Ph); δ 6.8-7.8 (ArH).

Biological properties: Compounds 3, 4, 7 and 8 were screened for antiameobic and antifungal activities against *Aspergillus flavus* using poison food technique⁷. Compound 8 was found active against *Entamoeba histolytica* at a dose of 250 μ g ml⁻¹ while others were marginally active. All the four compounds showed significant activity against *A. flavus* using potato-dextrose-agar medium.

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